

Formation of Boxy/Peanut-Shaped
Bulges --- Theoretical/Simulation
Perspective

Juntai Shen

Shanghai Jiao Tong University (SJTU)

上海交通大學
SHANGHAI JIAO TONG UNIVERSITY

Boxy Peanut-Shaped (BPS) Bulges

- Milky Way
- External galaxies
 - ~45% of edge-on disks have BPS bulges (Lutticke et al. '00)
 - Also M31 (Beaton & Athanassoula '06, Blana+ '18; also see **poster by Zi-Xuan Feng**)

How to form a BPS bulge?

The most straightforward mechanism

Buckling/bending instability

Bending waves: basics

- Basic idea (Toomre '66, Binney & Tremaine '08)

- Behavior of bending waves in an infinite, self-gravitating thin sheet embedded in a halo/bulge potential ($\frac{1}{2}\nu_{\text{ext}}^2 z^2$)

$$z_s(x, t) \sim z_0 e^{i(kx - \omega t)}$$

- A planar bending wave travelling in the horizontal (x) direction

- If no horizontal motions:

$$\frac{d^2 z_s}{dt^2} = \frac{\partial^2 z_s}{\partial t^2} = F_z = -2\pi G \Sigma |k| z_s - \nu_{\text{ext}}^2 z_s$$

- Restoring forces due to **disk self-gravity** and **external halo potential**, respectively

- Dispersion relation

$$\omega^2 = \nu_{\text{ext}}^2 + 2\pi G \Sigma |k|$$

- Bending waves in an infinite thin sheet are **always stable if there are no horizontal random motions**

Bending waves: with random motions

- If random motions in the x-y plane

$$\frac{\partial^2 z_s}{\partial t^2} + \sigma_x^2 \frac{\partial^2 z_s}{\partial x^2} = F_z(x, t) = -2\pi G \Sigma |k| z_s.$$

- Dispersion relation for an isolated disk ($\nu_{\text{ext}} = 0$)

random motion: destabilizing bending waves.

$$\omega^2 = 2\pi G \Sigma |k| - \sigma^2 k^2 \quad (\text{opposite to Jeans})$$

- The **buckling instability sets in** when

gravitational restoring force

<

Centrifugal force $\sigma^2/\lambda \cdot (h/\lambda)$
(as stars pass over the corrugations)

short wave unstable:

$$\lambda < \lambda_J \equiv \frac{\sigma^2}{G \Sigma}$$

(opposite to Jeans)

- Disk self-gravity tends to destabilize density waves but stabilizes bending waves, while **velocity dispersion stabilizes density waves but destabilizes bending waves!**
- A disk embedded in a massive halo ($\nu_{\text{ext}} \neq 0$) will be more stable than an isolated disk

Buckling instability

- Closely related to the **fire-hose instability**
 - Hanging hose begins to oscillate violently when a strong flow of water passes through it
- Kelvin-Helmholtz instability
 - Two incompressible fluids (one floating atop the other) are in relative horizontal motion.
- Razor-thin → slab with finite thickness
- valid only for $\lambda >$ actual thickness of the slab

$$\lambda_b = \lambda_J \equiv \sigma_x^2 / (G\Sigma) > z_0 \sim \sigma_z^2 / (G\Sigma)$$

Instability suppressed when $\sigma_z / \sigma_x >$ threshold value

- Araki (1987) infinite, isothermal slab:

$$\text{Instability condition: } \sigma_z / \sigma_x \lesssim \mathbf{0.3}$$

- In realistic axisymmetric disks **even higher vertical/in-plane ratio (~0.6) is needed to avoid the buckling instability** (Merritt & Sellwood '94, Sellwood & Merritt '94)

Buckling instability may help shaping ellipticals

- Hot stellar systems (giant ellipticals) also suffer from buckling instability if too flat
 - → **buckling instability limits their flattening**
- Possibly explains the **absence of ellipticals flatter than E6/E7** (Fridman & Polyachenko 1984)

Merritt & Hernquist (1991)

Buckling instability in a barred galaxy

- Axisymmetric disk \rightarrow formation of a bar
- **Bar formation makes a disk more susceptible to the buckling instability**
 - Rapid streaming motion along the bar major axis increases the effective horizontal vel dispersion, thus compromising

Stability condition: $\sigma_z/\sigma \gtrsim 0.6$

- Thin bar \rightarrow out-of-plane buckling instability
 - Raha+ ('91), also Combes & Sanders ('81); Combes+ ('90)
 - Violent, rapid (100s Mrs)

Raha+ ('91)

Recurrent buckling

- Buckling instability also weakens the bar to some extent
- A bar can grow secularly after the buckling
- can even trigger a secondary buckling
- Milder, persists for a longer period (3 Gyr)

Martinez-Valpuesta+ ('06)

The Galactic bulge: a tale of two instabilities

- Recent surveys + dynamical modelling
 - BRAVA; ARGOS; APOGEE; GIBS; VVV; Gaia-ESO
- A simple buckled bar model can match survey data very well in many aspects
- **Physical mechanism: a tale of two instabilities!**
- **Bar-forming instability** (in-plane) → **buckling instability** (vertical) → saturation → boxy bulge
- Dynamical properties of the bar (bar angle, pattern speed, axial ratio, bar length) are roughly consistent with independent studies
 - also newer Milky Way surrogate Tepper-Garcia+ ('21) etc
- Shaped by internal instabilities of a precursor disk, instead of major mergers?

Shen+ 2010; Ness+ 2013

BPS bulge from the buckling instability

- A peanut naturally predicted by a buckled bar after buckling instability saturates in 100s Myr
 - Fraction of bars and BPS bulges at $z=0$ seems to match ($\sim 70\%$)
 - Lutticke+ '00, Erwin+ '17, Eskridge '00, Sheth+ '08
- **MW's boxy bulge \approx central thickened bar** seen nearly end-on ($20\text{-}30^\circ$)
 - Only the central bar thickens
 - **A buckled bar = central peanut + outer thin part**
 - Athanassoula ('05)
 - Boxy part (peanut shape) ~ 2 kpc, **much less extended than the bar itself**
 - Also true in external galaxies (Erwin+ '17)

Li & Shen (2015)

BPS bulge + long thin bar in MW

- Long thin bar in MW (Benjamin+ '05; Cabrera-Lavers+ '07)
- Galactic boxy bulge and long bar reconstructed by combining various NIR surveys
 - *Top*: the inner Galaxy in solar perspective
 - *Middle*: Face-on projection of best-fitting red clump star count model
 - *Bottom*: side-on view of the bar/bulge

BPS → bimodal dist. of stars in MW bulge

- Along different lines of sight, distance of “standard candles” (red clump stars) splits into two groups (McWilliam & Zoccali '10) → “X-shape” structure, “inconsistent with the tilted bar morphology”
 - “X-shaped” structure can be explained by a boxy bulge (Li & Shen '12)
 - fainter and brighter RCs do have different proper motions
 - i.e. they are indeed at different distances (Clarke+ '21)
- “X-shape”: a reflection of the central peanut (Li & Shen '15)
- Further evidence that **MW bulge formation is shaped mainly by internal dynamical instabilities**

McWilliam & Zoccali (2010) Nataf et al. (2010) Saito+ (2011) Li & Shen (2012)

Buckling phase “caught in action”

- Since buckling phase lasts for a few 100s Myr
- We ought to find currently buckling bars in action in a large galaxy sample! **Where are they?**

Chapter 10 Theoretical Models of the Galactic Bulge

Juntai Shen and Zhao-Yu Li

¹It is puzzling why no galaxy has been caught in the process of violent buckling as shown in Fig. 10.2. The saturation timescale of the buckling instability is very rapid (about a few hundred Myr), but **it is not short enough to miss out the violent buckling phase if one can observe thousands of edge-on barred galaxies.** Perhaps this implies that the buckling instability must have happened in the very early assembly stage of disc galaxies, which is much harder to observe.

- **Morphology:** asymmetric isophotes
 - Erwin & Debattista ('16): 2 out of 44
- Quadrupolar pattern in **stellar kinematics** (V_z)
 - Xiang+ (21): 5 out of 434 MaNGA galaxies
- Puzzle solved: these fractions are roughly consistent with the expectation that **buckling phase lasts for 0.5-1.0 Gyr**

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Effects of halo spin on BPS bulges

- BPS bulge is more pronounced ($\sim 20\%$) in higher-spin halos compared to nonrotating halos

Kataria & Shen ('22)

Can a BPS bulge form without violent buckling?

- Simulations: a significant gas mass fraction in the disc can suppress the buckling of bars?
 - Berentzen+ '98; Debattista '06; Berentzen '07; Wozniak & Michel-Dansac '09
 - However, no obs. evidence that the (atomic) gas mass ratio affects the presence of BPS bulges (Erwin & Debattista '07)

- Sellwood & Gerhard ('20): **two additional mechanisms.**
 - **Resonant passage:** bar orbits heated vertically by the passage through the 2:1 vertical resonance (Quillen et al. 2014)
 - **Resonant trapping:** a gradually increasing fraction of bar orbits trapped into the 2:1 vertical resonance
 - h_4 of the vertical velocity distribution may be a diagnostic?
 - **$h_4 < 0$ in the inner region of a buckled bar, while $h_4 > 0$ for the two more gradual mechanisms?**

Schwarzschild Modelling of barred galaxies

- Behzad's talk (application to barred S0 galaxy NGC 4371)
- Eugene Vasiliev's talk

Best-fitting model to MUSE/TIMER data

Tahmasebzadeh+ '22, '23

Schwarzschild Modelling of barred galaxies

- Orbital structure and **kinematic decomposition** of NGC 4371

Tahmasebzadeh+ '23 in prep

BP/X bar: x1, banana, periodic z-tube orbits

Classic bulge: non-resonant orbits with $\lambda_z < 0.5$

Outer disk: disk outside the bar ($\lambda_z > 0.5$)

Inner disk: disk inside the bar ($\lambda_z > 0.5$)

Summary

- Buckling instability can be understood from qualitative analysis of the bending waves dynamics
- Bar formation promotes the buckling instability
 - Strong bars tend to buckle
 - A tale of two sequential instabilities? (first bar instability \rightarrow buckling instability)
- Buckling instability is sufficient to make reasonable BPS bulges
 - Many observational aspects of MW's boxy bulge are well consistent with this scenario
 - Bar fraction matches fraction of BPS bulges at $z=0$
 - Buckling phase lasts for a few 100s Myrs --- some galaxies are observed in the act of buckling
- But is the buckling instability the only way to form a BPS bulge?
 - Other bar thickening mechanisms need to be understood better